

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS FOR AN INCREASED SUPPORT OF CITIZEN SCIENCE IN SPAIN

The European Citizen Science (ECS) Project aims to expand and strengthen the citizen science (CS) community in Europe through training and awareness-raising activities. Its advocacy goal is to promote the recognition of CS as a powerful tool for policymaking and a valuable research approach for scientific excellence and sustainable development across Europe.

As part of the ECS Project, on October 31st 2024, Science For Change and Fundación Ibercivis organized the event "**Co-creating Change: Citizen Science, Impact, and National Policies**" hosted by Fundación Cotec (Madrid, Spain). This event brought together over 30 stakeholders from the quadruple helix (4H) to discuss Spain's and Europe's progress in mainstreaming CS. Key attendees included the Secretary of State for Research, Eva Ortega-Paino; the Director of the Spanish Foundation for Science and Technology (FECYT), Izaskun Lacunza; the Director of Cotec, Jorge Barrero; the ECS Project Officer, Irina Tiron; Francisco Castejón, from the Spanish Nuclear Safety Council (CSN); and the Ibercivis Director, Francisco Sanz. Tit Neubauer, from Slovenia's Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation, and the ECS Ambassador in Romania, Lucrina Stefanescu, shared notable examples of enhanced national support for CS. The event was conducted and organised by Rosa Arias, CEO & Founder at Science for Change and ECSA's Board of Directors; Fermín Serrano, Chair of the the ECSA Working Group on Policy, Strategy and Partnerships, ECS partner from Ibercivis; and by Mireia Ros, ECS project manager at Science for Change.

Another central feature of the event was a co-creation workshop, fostering collaboration of 4H stakeholders to develop policy recommendations aimed at enhancing support for CS and advancing open science initiatives at the national level in Spain. We want to thank all speakers and participants for their contribution during the event and for the revision of this policy brief.

WHAT IS CITIZEN SCIENCE

As defined by the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA): *Citizen science, in general, means the participation of the public in science and research. It is an open and inclusive approach, with key characteristics including: (1) **citizens are actively involved in research**; and (2) there is a **genuine science outcome**, such as new scientific knowledge, conservation action or policy change.*

Some of the benefits of CS are that it contributes to the democratization of scientific research by increasing public awareness of societal challenges, such as climate change and biodiversity conservation, trust in science, scientific literacy, while fostering critical thinking and behavioural change. Involving society in research allows for the collection of larger volumes of data, making information more accessible and relevant to real-world needs. This approach amplifies diverse voices and ensures that research reflects the concerns of all community members.

METHODOLOGY

The co-creation workshop's main objective was to **develop policy recommendations** tailored to Spain's research and innovation context for enhanced support of CS. The co-creation process focused on **understanding 4-H stakeholders' motivations** for engaging with CS, **identifying challenges**, and **developing actionable policy solutions**.

The methodology for co-creating policy recommendations to enhance and embed CS into national schemes within EU Member States is based on the Mutual Learning Exercise (MLE) on Citizen Science led by the European Commission.

It follows the backcasting planning approach, starting with future goals and working backwards to identify practical steps towards achieving them based on the country's baseline. Both the future goals and the baseline analysis were provided during the theoretical part of the policy event.

Fig 1. Backcasting in the MLE, following the A-B-C-D method developed by The Natural Step

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THE CASE OF SLOVENIA

Slovenia, still in the early stages of integrating CS into national policies, set ambitious goals for 2030 based on the recommendations from the 2022 MLE on CS. These objectives included **establishing a CS Observatory through the creation of** a national network connected internationally, and the development of a database to track related projects, initiatives, and infrastructures. Another key goal was to focus on **integrating CS into Research and Innovation (R&I)**, promoting CS within the research community, creating guidelines for practitioners, and organizing annual national events.

By 2024, Slovenia has made significant progress, such as **creating a national CS network**, launching a **database of CS projects and initiatives**, organizing key CS events such as an **Annual National CS event**, and **connecting with the <https://eu-citizen.science/> platform**.

THE CASE OF ROMANIA

Romania demonstrates strong commitment to CS through its **National Strategy on Research, Innovation, and Smart Specialization (2022-2027)**, which explicitly supports citizen participation in research. In 2022, it launched the **White Paper on the Transition to Open Science (2023-2030)**, aligning national policies with international Open Science frameworks. The **National Plan for Research, Development, and Innovation (2022-2027)** further reinforces this by fostering dialogue between science and society through the Science and Society Program.

By 2024, Babeş-Bolyai University launched its first **Citizen Science platform**, supported by a grant from the Ministry of Education via the National Council for the Financing of Higher Education (CNFIS). The university also introduced **internal CS grants and updated research evaluation metrics** to further support CS. Additionally, the **Romanian Open Science Portal** developed by the Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, and Innovation Funding (**UEFISCDI**) launched in 2022, connecting national and international Open Science initiatives.

THE CASE OF SPAIN

Spain has over 20 years of experience in citizen science (CS), with multiple research public and private actors leading CS initiatives. The **Law of Science, Technology, and Innovation (Law 17/2022)** explicitly mentions public engagement, while the **Organic Law of the University System (Law 2/2023)** supports open science and CS under its article 12. The **National Strategy on Open Science (2023-2027)** also recognizes CS as one of its six pillars of open science, advocating for open access to research results and citizen involvement throughout the research process.

Institutionally, **the Ministry of Science has been part of Fundación Ibercivis since 2012**, positioning it as Spain's national institution dedicated to running, supporting, and analyzing CS projects. In 2016, **FECYT funded the creation of the Spanish National Observatory of CS**, which is now led by Fundación Ibercivis, and maintained largely by interested stakeholders and volunteers, with limited ongoing support. It visualises the main CS initiatives and actors in Spain.

In terms of dedicated funding for CS, continuous support has been translated into the **creation of a specific call funding CS** as part of the strategic plan of FECYT, which since 2018, has funded 150-200 small projects (around €10-30k each). In 2022, the former Ministry of Universities (currently integrated under the Ministry of Science) **increased the support through a new line of projects**, to be done in consortium with a university or research center, with a new line of funding of €400.000. Despite these efforts, **many CS projects still rely on European funding**, as sustaining existing initiatives remains challenging, with most calls prioritizing new projects.

Spain's favorable climate, diverse landscapes, and strong societal traditions of outdoor collaboration provide a unique advantage for CS, enabling a wide range of initiatives, particularly in environmental monitoring and biodiversity research. However, **Spain's quasi-federal governance structure leads to significant regional variations** in legislative frameworks, funding mechanisms, and institutional support for CS. Therefore, ensuring alignment between national and regional efforts is crucial for the long-term sustainability of CS in the country.

On the academic front, the new ANECA President (the Spanish Agency for Evaluation and Accreditation) is strongly supporting CS, **aligning with European initiatives like the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA)**. Spanish researchers are working hard to prove the value of the practice to produce scientific, policy and societal impact in all scientific fields, with a continuously growing number of CS publications in terms of topics, methods, scope, and inclusiveness.

Additionally, the recently completed **Impactos-CC** project has delivered a **national report** highly relevant to **contextualizing impact reporting in CS**. This initiative contributes to strengthening the evidence base for CS, reinforcing its role in policy and decision-making.

During the practical segment of the session, stakeholders from 4H sectors identified several key motivations and challenges for enhancing the support of CS within Spain's national framework.

MOTIVATIONS

Promote science education and scientific evidence

CS is viewed as an opportunity to transform and disseminate scientific culture and educate the general public—not only on science itself, but also on broader topics of societal interest, also fostering critical thinking. This, in turn, helps counter misinformation and strengthens democratic engagement with institutions and policies.

Knowledge Generation

CS is a powerful approach for producing actionable data that directly addresses societal challenges while amplifying its impact through locally grounded insights. By integrating community knowledge, CS favors that research, development, and innovation (RDI) align with real-world needs. Additionally, it fosters behavioral change and generates scientifically rigorous knowledge that is both socially relevant and policy-informing.

Advocacy

Citizens and social economy organizations view CS as a powerful tool to influence political decisions and address societal needs, for vulnerable groups, linking it to social justice. However, policymakers and the private sector focus on using CS for trust-building and marketing rather than solving real societal problems.

Institutional positioning

CS's growing popularity in Europe offers institutions a chance to appear modern, enhance their image, demonstrate social responsibility, and potentially gain prestige, revenues, or electoral support.

Financial motivations

Public administration and academia see CS as a low-cost way to secure grants, but this overlooks its need for significant resources in management and engagement, reflecting a misunderstanding of its complexity.

CHALLENGES AND BARRIERS

Resource constraints

Limited resources due to unstable funding driven by shifting political priorities and short-term grants. This often results in scattered initiatives that lack coordination and integration, leading to mid-term inefficiencies and participant disengagement, as projects don't last long enough to build sustained communities. Additionally, CS is sometimes seen as a financial burden, with concerns about data quality, publication costs, and unclear economic incentives for the private sector.

Complexity of implementation

CS projects are perceived as complex in terms of sustaining participant engagement and managing personal data. Citizens also report insecurity about participating due to limited training or technological barriers.

Lack of awareness and understanding

There is insufficient understanding of CS within public administration, the private sector, and even among citizens, which hinders participation and support.

Lack of incentives and recognition

While researchers in Spain already have incentives for CS participation through the current evaluation framework under ANECA, aligning with advancements made under the CoARA, there remains a lack of clear incentives for involvement in CS in both the public and private sectors.

After the identification of challenges followed the cocreation of policy solutions for each one of them, which in turn led to their prioritization and finding of solutions that benefit most stakeholders.

SOLUTIONS AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the motivations, challenges, and barriers identified, the following key solutions were prioritized to mainstream citizen science in Spain:

Impact Reporting

Reporting the impact of CS is a critical strategy to demonstrate its value to various stakeholders. By aligning CS with the interests of different groups, its potential to save resources, its broader economic benefits, and ability to improve scientific literacy can be highlighted, making it easier to justify public funding. Furthermore, impact reporting helps to demonstrate the long-term benefits of CS beyond political cycles. Showing evidence of sustained positive impact can support CS as a more attractive option for policymakers compared to traditional research approaches.

Raising Awareness and Understanding of CS

There is a significant gap in understanding what CS entails, including its processes, resource needs, and potential impacts. Raising awareness and promoting a deeper understanding of CS is therefore essential. Tailored awareness campaigns should target specific stakeholders—ministries might focus on funding strategies, while companies could be engaged through market-based incentives.

Expanding Access to Citizen Science

The lack of knowledge about how to engage with CS projects is another key barrier, especially for citizens. Creating centralized platforms or databases that list ongoing CS projects and provide clear guidance on how to get involved could help mitigate this. Additionally, implementing conciliation policies to allow citizens with limited time or resources to participate would foster inclusion and increase engagement, especially among those who might otherwise be excluded from CS initiatives.

SOLUTIONS AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

Training, Capacity Building and Academic Recognition

In addition to addressing the perceived complexity of CS and the misunderstandings about the effort and resources required to carry out CS projects, strengthening the capacity of 4-H stakeholders in CS has the potential to turn CS into a tool for aligning the interests of broader society with political agendas. For that, training and capacity building of researchers involved and academic recognition of the practice are considered vital for its mainstreaming and for ensuring the quality of data collected in CS.

Protocols and Open Data Infrastructure

To address the complexity and perceived inaccessibility of CS, it is essential to develop public-use protocols and establish user-friendly, open data repositories that are easily accessible. These tools should cater to the needs of citizen science project leaders, but also of policymakers and the private sector, encouraging broader participation and facilitating practical application of CS.

Incentives for Companies and Academia

Providing targeted incentives for companies and academic institutions to prioritize CS over traditional research practices is crucial for fostering engagement. These could include tax breaks or dedicated funding opportunities for CS projects. Public-private partnerships can also play a role by aligning CS with corporate social responsibility (CSR) or environmental, social, and governance (ESG) goals, allowing companies to address societal challenges while meeting sustainability targets. In academia, incentives can be integrated by redefining research funding KPIs and evaluation criteria within academic assessment frameworks, following the work from COARA.

Leveraging the Growing Recognition of CS as Innovative Practice

The increasing recognition of CS as an innovative and forward-thinking practice across Europe offers a valuable opportunity to motivate both policymakers and the private sector to invest in it. However, it is crucial to emphasize the intrinsic value of CS—particularly its ability to promote science education, civic engagement, behavioural change, to increase trust in science and to foster critical thinking to address complex societal issues—beyond its use as a marketing tool or a means to enhance institutional image and public trust.

POLICY BRIEF DETAILS

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Authors:

Mireia Ros (Science for Change), Rosa Arias (Science for Change), Fermín Serrano Sanz (Fundación Ibercivis), Héloïse Vilaseca (Science for Change)

Speakers and contributors:

Eva Ortega-Paíno (Secretary of State for Research, Spanish Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities), Izaskun Lacunza (FECYT, Director), Jorge Barrero (Cotec, Director), Francisco Castejón (Spanish Council for Nuclear Security, CSN), Irina Tiron (Research Executive Agency, ECS Project Officer), Tit Neubauer (Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation), Lucrina Stefanescu (Babes-Bolyai University, ECS Ambassador in Romania), Rosa Arias (Science for Change, CEO & Founder), Mireia Ros (Science for Change, ECS Project Manager), Francisco Sanz (Fundación Ibercivis, Executive Director), Fermín Serrano Sanz (Fundación Ibercivis, Project Manager).

4H contributors to the co-creation activities (publication permission granted only):

Víctor Castelo Gutiérrez (Fundación Ibercivis), Renata Kubus (Universidad Complutense de Madrid), M.^a del Carmen Mínguez García (Universidad Complutense de Madrid), Sandra Obispo Legazpe (Universidad Autónoma de Madrid), Alejandro Sánchez de Miguel (Universidad Complutense de Madrid), Alfonso Vallés Sales (Universidad Fernando Pessoa Canarias)